

CONTROLLABLE DEEP MELODY GENERATION VIA HIERARCHICAL MUSIC STRUCTURE REPRESENTATION

Shuqi Dai **Zeyu Jin** **Celso Gomes** **Roger B. Dannenberg**
Carnegie Mellon university Adobe Inc. Adobe Inc. Carnegie Mellon University
shuqid@cs.cmu.edu zej@adobe.com cegomes@adobe.com rbd@cs.cmu.edu

ABSTRACT

Recent advances in deep learning have expanded possibilities to generate music, but generating a customizable full piece of music with consistent long-term structure remains a challenge. This paper introduces *MusicFrameworks*, a hierarchical music structure representation and a multi-step generative process to create a full-length melody guided by long-term repetitive structure, chord, melodic contour, and rhythm constraints. We first organize the full melody with section and phrase-level structure. To generate melody in each phrase, we generate rhythm and basic melody using two separate transformer-based networks, and then generate the melody conditioned on the basic melody, rhythm and chords in an auto-regressive manner. By factoring music generation into sub-problems, our approach allows simpler models and requires less data. To customize or add variety, one can alter chords, basic melody, and rhythm structure in the music frameworks, letting our networks generate the melody accordingly. Additionally, we introduce new features to encode musical positional information, rhythm patterns, and melodic contours based on musical domain knowledge. A listening test reveals that melodies generated by our method are rated as good as or better than human-composed music in the POP909 dataset about half the time.

1. INTRODUCTION

Music generation is an important component of computational and AI creativity, leading to many potential applications including automatic background music generation for video, music improvisation in human-computer music performance and customizing stylistic music for individual music therapy, to name a few. While works such as MelNet [1] and JukeBox [2] have demonstrated a degree of success in generating music in the audio domain, the majority of the work is in the symbolic domain, i.e., the score, as this is the most fundamental representation of music composition. Research has tackled this question from many angles, including monophonic melody genera-

tion [3], polyphonic performance generation [4] and drum pattern generation [5]. This paper focuses on melody generation, a crucial component in music writing practice.

Recently, deep learning has demonstrated success in capturing implicit rules about music from the data, compared to conventional rule-based and statistical methods [4, 6, 7]. However, there are three problems that are difficult to address: (1) Modeling larger scale music structure and multiple levels of repetition as seen in popular songs, (2) Controllability to match music to video or create desired tempo, styles, and mood, and (3) Scarcity of training data due to limited curated and machine-readable compositions, especially in a given style. Since humans can imitate music styles with just a few samples, there is reason to believe there exists a solution that enables music generation with few samples as well.

We aim to explore automatic melody generation with multiple levels of structure awareness and controllability. Our focus is on (1) addressing structural consistency inside a phrase and on the global scale, and (2) giving explicit control to users to manipulate melody contour and rhythm structure directly. Our solution, *MusicFrameworks*, is based on the design of hierarchical music representations we call *music frameworks* inspired by Hiller and Ames [8]. A music framework is an abstract hierarchical description of a song, including high-level music structure such as repeated sections and phrases, and lower-level representations such as rhythm structure and melodic contour. The idea is to represent a piece of music by music frameworks, and then learn to generate melodies from music frameworks. Controllability is achieved by editing the music frameworks at any level (song, section and phrase); we also present methods that generate these representations from scratch. *MusicFrameworks* can create long-term music structures, including repetition, by factoring music generation into sub-problems, allowing simpler models and requiring less data.

Evaluations of the *MusicFrameworks* approach include objective measures to show expected behavior and subjective assessments. We compare human-composed melodies and melodies generated under various conditions to study the effectiveness of music frameworks. We summarize our contributions as follows: (1) devising a hierarchical music structure representation and approach called *MusicFrameworks* capable of capturing repetitive structure at multiple levels, (2) enabling controllability at multiple levels of abstraction through music frameworks, (3) a set of methods

that analyze a song to derive music frameworks that can be used in music imitation and subsequent deep learning processes, (4) a set of neural networks that generate a song using the *MusicFrameworks* approach, (5) useful musical features and encodings to introduce musical inductive biases into deep learning, (6) comparison of different deep learning architectures for relatively small amounts of training data and a sizable listening test evaluating the musicality of our method against human-composed music.

2. RELATED WORK

Automation of music composition with computers can be traced back to 1957 [9]. Long before representation learning, musicians looked for models that explain the generative process of music [8]. Early music generation systems often relied on generative rules or constraint satisfaction [8, 10–12]. Subsequent approaches replaced human learning of rules with machine learning, such as statistical models [13] and connectionist approaches [14]. Now, deep learning has emerged as one of the most powerful tools to encode implicit rules from data [4, 15–18].

One challenge of music modelling is capturing repetitive patterns and long-term dependencies. There are a few models using rule-based and statistical methods to construct long-term repetitive structure in classical music [19] and pop music [20, 21]. Machine learning models with memory and the ability to associate context have also been popular in this area and include LSTMs and Transformers [4, 6, 22, 23], which operate by generating music one or a few notes at a time, based on information from previously generated notes. These models enable free generation and motif continuation, but it is difficult to control the generated content. StructureNet [3], PopMNet [24] and Racchmaninof [19] are more closely related to our work in that they introduce explicit models for music structure.

Another thread of work enables a degree of controllability by modeling the distribution of music via an intermediate representation (embedding). One such approach is to use Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) to model the distribution of music [25–27]. GANs learn a mapping from a point z sampled from a prior distribution to an instance of generated music x and hence represents the distribution of music with z . Another method is the Autoencoder, consisting of an encoder transforming music x into embedding z and a decoder that reconstructs music x again from embedding z . The most popular models are Variational Auto-Encoders (VAE) and their variants [28–33]. These models can be controlled by manipulating the embedding, for example, mix-and-matching embeddings of different pitch contours and rhythms [29, 30, 34]. However, a high-dimensional continuous vector has limited interpretability and thus is difficult for a user to control; it is also difficult to model full-length music with a simple fixed-length representation. In contrast, our approach uses a hierarchical music representation (i.e., *music framework*) as an “embedding” of music that encodes long-term dependency in a form that is both interpretable and controllable.

Figure 1. Architecture of *MusicFrameworks*.

Figure 2. An example music framework.

3. METHOD

We describe a controllable melody generation system that uses hierarchical music representation to generate full-length pop song melodies with multi-level repetition and structure. As shown in Figure 1, a song is input in MIDI format. We analyze its *music framework*, which is an abstracted description of the music ideas of the input song. Then we use the music framework to generate a new song with deep learning models.

Our work is with pop music because structures are relatively simple and listeners are generally familiar with the style and thus able to evaluate compositions. We use a Chinese pop song dataset, POP909 [35], and use its cleaned version [36] (with more labeling and corrections) for training and testing in this paper. We further transpose all the major songs’ key signatures into C major. We use integers 1–15 to represent scale degrees in C3–C5, and 0 to represent a rest. For rhythm, we use the 16th note as the minimum unit. A note in the melody is represented as (p, d) , where p is the pitch number from 0 to 15, and d is duration in sixteenths. For chord progressions, we use integers 1–7 to represent seven scale degree chords in the major mode. (We currently work only with triads, and convert seventh chords into corresponding triads).

3.1 Music Frameworks Analysis

As shown in Figure 2, a music framework contains two parts: (1) section and phrase-level structure analysis re-

Figure 3. An example melody and its basic melody. The basic rhythm form also appears below the original melody as “a,0.38 b,0.06, ...” indicating similarity and complexity.

Figure 4. Generation process from music frameworks within each phrase.

sults; (2) basic melody and basic rhythm form within each phrase. A phrase is a small-scale segment that usually ranges from 4 to 16 measures. Phrases can be repeated as in AABBB shown in Figure 2. Sections contain multiple phrases, e.g., the illustrated song has an intro, a main theme section (phrase A as verse and phrase B as chorus), a bridge section followed by a repeat of the theme, and an outro section, which is a typical pop song structure. We extract the section and phrase structure based on finding approximate repetitions following the work of [36].

Within each phrase, the *basic melody* is an abstraction of melody and contour. Basic melody is a sequence of half notes representing the most common pitch in each 2-beat segment of the original phrase (see Figure 3). The *basic rhythm form* consists of a per-measure descriptor with two components: a pattern label based on a rhythm similarity measure [36] (measures with matching labels are similar) and a numerical rhythmic complexity, which is simply the number of notes divided by 16.

With the analysis algorithm, we can process a music dataset such as POP909 for subsequent machine learning and music generation. The music frameworks enable controllability via examples in which a user can also mix and match different music frameworks from multiple songs. For example, a new song can be generated using the structure from song A, basic melody from song B, and basic rhythm form from song C. Users can also edit or directly create a music framework for even greater control. Alternatively, we also created generative algorithms to create new music frameworks without any user intervention as described in subsequent sections.

3.2 Generation Using Music Frameworks

At the top level, section and phrase structure can be provided by a user or simply selected from a library of already analyzed data. We considered several options for imitation at this top level: (1) copy the first several measures of melody from the previously generated phrase (teacher forcing mode) and then complete the current phrase; (2) use the same or similar basic melody from the previous phrase to generate an altered melody with a similar melodic contour; (3) use the same or similar basic rhythm form of the previous phrase to generate a similar rhythm. These options leave room for users to customize their personal preferences. In this study, we forgo all human control by randomly choosing between the first and second option.

At the phrase level, as shown in Figure 4, we first generate a basic melody (or a human provides one). Next, we

generate rhythm using the basic rhythm form. Finally, we generate a new melody given the basic melody, generated rhythm, and chords copied from the input song.

3.2.1 Basic Melody Generation

We use an auto-regressive approach to generate basic melodies. The input $x_i = (\text{pos}_i, c_i, \dots)$ ($i \in 1, \dots, n$) is a set of features that guides basic melody generation where pos_i is the positional feature of the i^{th} note and c_i represents contextual chord information (neighboring chords). We denote p_i of the i^{th} note. Here we fix the duration of each note in the basic melody to the half-note as in the analysis algorithm described in Section 3.1. c_i contains the previous, current and next chords and their lengths for the i^{th} note. pos_i includes the position of the i^{th} note in the current phrase and a long-term positional feature indicating whether the current phrase is at the end of a section or not.

3.2.2 Network Architecture

We use an auto-regressive model based on Transformer and LSTM. The architecture (Figure 5) consists of an encoder and a decoder. The encoder has two layers of transformers that learn a feature representation of the inputs (e.g. positional encodings and chords). The decoder concatenates the encoded representation and the last predicted note as input and passes them through one unidirectional LSTM followed by two layers of 1D convolutions of kernel size 1. Both the input and the last predicted notes to the decoder are passed through a projection layer (aka. a dense layer) respectively before they are processed by the network. The final output is the next note predicted by the decoder via categorical distribution $Pr(p_i|X, p_1, \dots, p_{i-1})$. We also tried using other deep neural network architectures such as a pre-trained full Transformer with random masking (described in Section 4.1) for comparison.

3.2.3 Sampling with Dynamic Time Warping Control

In the sampling stage, we tried three ways to autoregressively generate the basic melody sequence: (1) randomly sample from the estimated posterior distribution of p_i at each step; (2) randomly sample 100 generated sequences and pick the one with highest overall estimated probability; (3) beam search sampling according to the estimated probability. Apart from the above three sampling methods, we also want to control the basic melody contour shape in order to generate similar or repeated phrases. We use a melody contour rating function (based on Dynamic Time Warping) [21] to estimate the contour similarity between two basic melodies. When we want to generate a repetition phrase that has a similar basic melody compared to a previous phrase, we estimate the contour similarity rating between the generated basic melody and the reference basic melody. We only accept basic melodies with a similarity above a threshold of 0.7.

3.2.4 Realized Rhythm Generation

We now turn to the lower level of music generation that transforms music frameworks into realized songs. The first

Figure 5. Transformer-LSTM architecture for melody, basic melody and rhythmic pattern generation.

step is to determine the note onsets, namely the rhythm. Instead of generating note onset time one by one, we generate 2-beat rhythm patterns, which more readily encode rhythmic patterns and metrical structure. It is also easier to model (and apparently to learn) similarity using rhythm patterns than with sequences of individual durations.

We generate 2-beat patterns sequentially under the control of a basic rhythm form. There are 256 possible rhythm patterns with a 2-beat length using our smallest subdivision of sixteenthths. For each rhythm pattern r_i , the input of the rhythm generation model is $x_i = (r_{i-1}, \text{brf}_i, \text{pos}_i)$, where r_{i-1} is the previously generated rhythm pattern, brf_i is the index of the first measure similar to it (or the current measure if there is no previous reference) and the current measure complexity; pos_i contains three positional components: (1) the position of the i^{th} pattern in the current phrase; (2) a long-term positional feature indicating whether the current phrase is at the end of a section or not; (3) whether the i^{th} rhythm pattern starts at the barline or not. We also use a Transformer-LSTM architecture (Figure 5), but with different model settings (size). In the sampling stage, we use beam search.

3.2.5 Realized Melody Generation

We generate melody from a basic melody, a rhythm and a chord progression using another Transformer-LSTM architecture similar to generating basic melody in Figure 5. In this case, the index i represents the i^{th} note determined by the rhythm. The input feature x_i also includes the current note’s duration, the current chord, the basic melody pitch, and three positional features for multiple-level structure guidance: the two positional features for basic melody generation (Section 3.2.1) and the offset of the current note within the current measure. We also experimented with other deep neural network architectures described in Section 4.1 for comparison. To sample a good sounding melody, we randomly generate 100 sequences by sampling

	Basic Melody	Rhythm	Melody
Trans-LSTM	38.7%	50.1%	55.2%
LSTM	39.8%	43.6%	51.2%
Transformer	30.9%	25.8%	39.3%
No M.F.	NA	33.1%	37.4%

Table 1. Validation Accuracy of different model architectures. “No M.F.” means no music frameworks used here.

the autoregressive model. We pick the one with the highest overall estimated probability. More details about the network are in Section 4.1.

4. EXPERIMENT AND EVALUATION

4.1 Model Evaluation and Comparison

As a model-selection study, we compared the ability of different deep neural network architectures implementing *MusicFrameworks* to predict the next element in the sequence. *Basic Melody Accuracy* is the percent of correct predictions of the next pitch of the basic melody (half notes). *Rhythm Accuracy* is the percent of correctly predicted 2-beat rhythm patterns. *Melody Accuracy* is the accuracy of next pitch prediction.

We used 4188 phrases from 528 songs in major mode from the POP909 dataset, using 90% of them as training data and the other 10% for validation. The first line in Table 1 represents the Transformer-LSTM models introduced in Section 3. In all three networks, the projection size and feed forward channels are 128; there are 8 heads in the multi-head encoder attention layer; LSTM hidden size is 64; dropout rate for basic melody and realized melody generation is 0.2, dropout rate for rhythm generation is 0.1; decoder input projection size is 8 for rhythm generation and 17 for others. For learning rate, we used the Adam optimizer with $\beta_1 = 0.9, \beta_2 = 0.99, \epsilon = 10^{-6}$, and the same formula in [22] to vary the learning rate over the course of training, with 2000 warmup steps.

We compared this model with several alternatives: the second model is a bi-directional LSTM followed by a unidirectional LSTM (model size is 64 in both). The third model is a Transformer with two layers of encoder and two layers of decoder (with same parameter settings as Transformer-LSTM), and we first pre-trained the encoder with 10% of random masking of input (similar to training in BERT [37]), and then trained the encoder and decoder together. No music frameworks (the fourth line) means generate without basic melody or basic rhythm form, using a Transformer-LSTM model. The results in Table 1 show that the Transformer-LSTM achieved the best accuracy. The full Transformer model performed poorly on this relatively small dataset due to overfitting. Also, in both rhythm and melody generation, the *MusicFrameworks* approach significantly improves the model accuracy.

4.2 Objective Evaluation

We use Transformer-LSTM model for all further evaluations. First, we examine whether music frameworks pro-

	R.Melody	Basic Melody	Rhythm
0	copy	copy	copy
1	gen	copy	copy
2	gen	gen	copy
3	gen	without	copy
4	gen	copy	gen with BRF
5	gen	copy	gen without BRF
6	gen	gen	gen with BRF

Table 2. Seven evaluation conditions. Group 0 is human-composed. R.Melody: realized melody; gen: generated from our system; BRF: Basic Rhythm Form; copy: directly copying that part from the human-composed song; without: not using music frameworks.

Figure 8. Rating distribution comparison for each paired groups. *For conditions 0 vs 1 and 0 vs 6, we removed the cases where the listeners indicated having heard the song before.

in test pairs “0 vs 1” and “0 vs 6” (and this is statistically significant), the preference test suggests that around half of the time the generated music is as good as or better than human-composed music, indicating the usability of the *MusicFrameworks* approach.

To understand the gap between our generated music and human-composed music, we look into the comments written by listeners and summarize our findings below:

- Since sampling is used in the generative process, there is a non-zero chance that a poor note choice may be generated. Though this does not affect the posterior probability significantly, it degrades the subjective rating. Repeated notes also have an adverse effect on musicality with a lesser influence on posterior probability.
- *MusicFrameworks* uses basic melody and rhythm form to control long-term dependency, i.e., phrases that are repetitions or imitations share the same or similar music framework; however, the generated melody has a chance to sound different due to the sampling process. A human listener can distinguish a human-composed song from a machine-generated song by listening for exact repetition.
- Basic melody provides more benefit for longer phrases. For short phrases (4-6 bars), generating melodies from

Figure 9. Preference distribution for each paired groups. *For conditions 0 vs 1 and 0 vs 6, we removed the cases where the listeners indicated having heard the song before.

- scratch is competitive with generating via basic melody.
- The human-composed songs used in this study are from the most popular ones in Chinese pop history. Even though raters may think they do not recognize the song, there is a chance that they have heard it. A large portion of the comments suggest that a lot of the test music sounds great and it was an enjoyable experience working on these surveys. However, some listeners point out that concentrating on relatively long excerpts was not a natural listening experience.

5. CONCLUSION

MusicFrameworks is a deep melody generation system using hierarchical music structure representations to enable a multi-level generative process. The key idea is to adopt an abstract representation, *music frameworks*, including long-term repetitive structures, phrase-level *basic melodies* and *basic rhythm forms*. We introduced analysis algorithms to obtain music frameworks from songs. We created a neural network that generates basic melody and additional networks to generate melodies. We also designed musical features and encodings to better introduce musical inductive bias into deep learning models.

Both objective and subjective evaluations show the importance of having music frameworks. About 50% of the generated songs are rated as good as or better than human-composed songs. Another important feature of the *MusicFrameworks* approach is *controllability* through manipulation of music frameworks, which can be freely edited and combined to guide compositions.

In the future, we hope to develop more intelligent ways to analyze music and music frameworks supporting a richer musical vocabulary, generation of harmony and polyphonic generation. We believe that hierarchical and structured representations offer a way to capture and imitate musical style, offering interesting new research opportunities.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank Dr. Stephen Neely for his insights on musical rhythm.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] S. Vasquez and M. Lewis, “Melnet: A generative model for audio in the frequency domain,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1906.01083*, 2019.
- [2] P. Dhariwal, H. Jun, C. Payne, J. W. Kim, A. Radford, and I. Sutskever, “Jukebox: A generative model for music,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2005.00341*, 2020.
- [3] G. Medeot, S. Cherla, K. Kosta, M. McVicar, S. Abdallah, M. Selvi, E. Newton-Rex, and K. Webster, “Structurenets: Inducing structure in generated melodies.” in *Proc. of 19th International Conference on Music Information Retrieval, ISMIR*, 2018, pp. 725–731.
- [4] C.-Z. A. Huang, A. Vaswani, J. Uszkoreit, N. Shazeer, I. Simon, C. Hawthorne, A. M. Dai, M. D. Hoffman, M. Dinculescu, and D. Eck, “Music transformer,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1809.04281*, 2018.
- [5] I.-C. Wei, C.-W. Wu, and L. Su, “Generating structured drum pattern using variational autoencoder and self-similarity matrix.” in *Proc. of 20th International Conference on Music Information Retrieval, ISMIR*, 2019, pp. 847–854.
- [6] Y.-S. Huang and Y.-H. Yang, “Pop music transformer: Generating music with rhythm and harmony,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2002.00212*, 2020.
- [7] S. H. Hakimi, N. Bhonker, and R. El-Yaniv, “Bebopnet: Deep neural models for personalized jazz improvisations,” in *Proc. of the 21st International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference, ISMIR*. ISMIR, 2020.
- [8] L. Hiller, C. Ames, and R. Franki, “Automated composition: An installation at the 1985 international exposition in tsukuba, japan,” *Perspectives of New Music*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 196–215, 1985.
- [9] L. Hiller and L. Isaacson, *Experimental Music: Composition with an Electronic Computer*. New York: McGraw-Hill, 1959.
- [10] D. Cope, *Computers and musical style*. Oxford University Press Oxford, 1991, vol. 6.
- [11] —, *The Algorithmic Composer*. AR Editions, Inc., 2000.
- [12] —, *Computer models of musical creativity*. MIT Press Cambridge, 2005.
- [13] W. Schulze and B. Van Der Merwe, “Music generation with markov models,” *IEEE Annals of the History of Computing*, vol. 18, no. 03, pp. 78–85, 2011.
- [14] N. Boulanger-Lewandowski, Y. Bengio, and P. Vincent, “Modeling temporal dependencies in high-dimensional sequences: Application to polyphonic music generation and transcription,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1206.6392*, 2012.
- [15] J.-P. Briot, G. Hadjeres, and F. Pachet, *Deep learning techniques for music generation*. Springer, 2019, vol. 10.
- [16] F. Liang, “Bachbot: Automatic composition in the style of bach chorales,” *University of Cambridge*, vol. 8, pp. 19–48, 2016.
- [17] G. Hadjeres, F. Pachet, and F. Nielsen, “Deepbach: a steerable model for bach chorales generation,” in *Proc. of the 34th International Conference on Machine Learning-Volume 70*. JMLR. org, 2017, pp. 1362–1371.
- [18] C.-Z. A. Huang, T. Cooijmans, A. Roberts, A. Courville, and D. Eck, “Counterpoint by convolution,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1903.07227*, 2019.
- [19] T. Collins and R. Laney, “Computer-generated stylistic compositions with long-term repetitive and phrasal structure,” *Journal of Creative Music Systems*, vol. 1, no. 2, 2017.
- [20] A. Elowsson and A. Friberg, “Algorithmic composition of popular music,” in *the 12th International Conference on Music Perception and Cognition and the 8th Triennial Conference of the European Society for the Cognitive Sciences of Music*, 2012, pp. 276–285.
- [21] S. Dai, X. Ma, Y. Wang, and R. B. Dannenberg, “Personalized popular music generation using imitation and structure,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2105.04709*, 2021.
- [22] A. Vaswani, N. Shazeer, N. Parmar, J. Uszkoreit, L. Jones, A. N. Gomez, Ł. Kaiser, and I. Polosukhin, “Attention is all you need,” in *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 2017, pp. 5998–6008.
- [23] C. Payne, “Musenet,” *OpenAI, openai.com/blog/musenet*, 2019.
- [24] J. Wu, X. Liu, X. Hu, and J. Zhu, “Popmnet: Generating structured pop music melodies using neural networks,” *Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 286, p. 103303, 2020.
- [25] I. Goodfellow, J. Pouget-Abadie, M. Mirza, B. Xu, D. Warde-Farley, S. Ozair, A. C. Courville, and Y. Bengio, “Generative adversarial networks,” *ArXiv*, vol. abs/1406.2661, 2014.
- [26] L. Yu, W. Zhang, J. Wang, and Y. Yu, “Seqgan: Sequence generative adversarial nets with policy gradient,” in *Thirty-First AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 2017.
- [27] H.-W. Dong, W.-Y. Hsiao, L.-C. Yang, and Y.-H. Yang, “Musegan: Multi-track sequential generative adversarial networks for symbolic music generation and accompaniment,” *Proc. of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 32, no. 1, Apr. 2018.
- [28] D. P. Kingma and M. Welling, “Auto-encoding variational bayes,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1312.6114*, 2013.

- [29] A. Roberts, J. Engel, C. Raffel, C. Hawthorne, and D. Eck, “A hierarchical latent vector model for learning long-term structure in music,” in *International Conference on Machine Learning*, 2018.
- [30] R. Yang, D. Wang, Z. Wang, T. Chen, J. Jiang, and G. Xia, “Deep music analogy via latent representation disentanglement,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1906.03626*, 2019.
- [31] H. H. Tan and D. Herremans, “Music fadernets: Controllable music generation based on high-level features via low-level feature modelling,” in *Proc. of 21st International Conference on Music Information Retrieval, ISMIR*, 2020.
- [32] L. Kawai, P. Esling, and T. Harada, “Attributes-aware deep music transformation,” in *Proc. of the 21st International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference, ISMIR*. ISMIR, 2020.
- [33] Z. Wang, D. Wang, Y. Zhang, and G. Xia, “Learning interpretable representation for controllable polyphonic music generation,” in *Proc. of 21st International Conference on Music Information Retrieval, ISMIR*, 2020.
- [34] K. Chen, C.-i. Wang, T. Berg-Kirkpatrick, and S. Dubnov, “Music sketchnet: Controllable music generation via factorized representations of pitch and rhythm,” in *Proc. of the 21st International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*. ISMIR, 2020.
- [35] Z. Wang*, K. Chen*, J. Jiang, Y. Zhang, M. Xu, S. Dai, G. Bin, and G. Xia, “Pop909: A pop-song dataset for music arrangement generation,” in *Proc. of 21st International Conference on Music Information Retrieval, ISMIR*, 2020.
- [36] S. Dai, H. Zhang, and R. B. Dannenberg, “Automatic analysis and influence of hierarchical structure on melody, rhythm and harmony in popular music,” in *Proc. of the 2020 Joint Conference on AI Music Creativity (CSMC-MuMe)*, 2020.
- [37] J. Devlin, M.-W. Chang, K. Lee, and K. Toutanova, “Bert: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding,” in *NAACL-HLT*, 2019.
- [38] S. Dai, H. Zhang, and R. B. Dannenberg, “Automatic analysis and influence of hierarchical structure on melody, rhythm and harmony in popular music,” in *in Proc. of the 2020 Joint Conference on AI Music Creativity (CSMC-MuMe 2020)*, 2020.